

MS18 Design of the service catalogue

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

MS18 Design of the service catalogue	3
1 Introduction.....	3
2 Context.....	3
3 “ENVRI catalogue of services” Task Force establishment.....	3
4 Progress on the design of the service catalogue	5
5 Proposed solution.....	5
6 Conclusion	6
7 Annex 1 – ENVRI-FAIR WP5 TF1 Catalogue Task Force Document	6
7.1 Objectives.....	6
7.2 Approach.....	7
7.2.1 Heterogeneity of Research Infrastructures.....	7
7.2.2 Achieving Interoperability.....	7
7.2.3 Rich Metadata Catalogue.....	7
7.2.4 EOSC Interoperability	7
7.2.5 Governance.....	7
7.3 Current work	8
7.3.1 Landscaping exercise.....	8
7.3.2 Capturing RIs heterogeneity	8
7.3.3 Convergence on the definition of “services”	8
7.3.4 Convergence on metadata required for the catalogue	8
7.4 Conclusion	8
7.5 Annex A – TF1 Members.....	8

MS18 Design of the service catalogue

1 Introduction

The main goal of this milestone is to report about the preliminary work for drafting the design of the ENVRI-FAIR service catalogue. The work was carried out mostly in the framework of the WP5 “ENVRI catalogue of services” Task Force.

2 Context

ENVRI-FAIR has two major objectives concerning the ENVRI RIs that have assets of interest:

- (1) To make those assets available FAIRly;
- (2) To make those assets visible to EOSC users and deployable to EOSC;

The canonical ENVRI catalog of assets (starting with services for EOSC compatibility) is thus an essential component of the ENVRI Hub architecture (and hence the relationship of the ENVRI Hub to the ENVRI RI e-Infrastructures) allowing:

- a) Interoperation among ENVRI RIs;
- b) Interoperation between ENVRI and EOSC.

3 “ENVRI catalogue of services” Task Force establishment

Following up the 20191030 Lund meeting, several task forces were set up in order to tackle specific aspects that actually cross several Tasks within WP5. One of these was the “ENVRI catalogue of services” task force1 (TF1). TF1 was established, and had one of its most important milestones at the ENVRI Week in Dresden, Germany, 3-7 February 2020, where a dedicated meeting was carried out, led by Daniele Bailo (INGV / EPOS-ERIC) and Keith Jeffery (BGS/UKRI).

During the meeting, the scenario was set up and relevant information was communicated to all the attendees, the problem of heterogeneous metadata from the various Research Infrastructures in ENVRI-FAIR was risen and discussed and the outcomes from previous projects (ENVRI and ENVRIplus) were presented. In particular the Canonical catalog approach was exposed, and the decision of setting up two catalogs with different metadata standards was presented (CKAN metadata as used in EUDAT, CERIF metadata as used in EPOS). Prototypes of both were produced in ENVRIplus, for RIs to examine and compare, but it led to no real conclusion.

Key requirements of the catalogue were also presented, mostly focusing on those deriving from the the FAIR principles (Identity, Rich metadata, Vocabularies, Licenses, Provenance etc.).

Key Objectives

Objectives of the task force were therefore presented and after some discussion they were agreed through a consensus-based procedures. The following objectives were defined:

TF1 Aims at:

- Creation of a catalogue of services within ENVRI-FAIR to support FAIRness
- Creation of a Catalogue that should be EOSC-ready
- Catalogue should not map all metadata, but describe services that provide access to data

Also, although the architecture was yet a premature topic, a generic architectural approach was presented and discussed in order to put the basis for fruitful discussion and agreements in the remote teleconference meetings envisaged after the ENVRI-WEEK. The architectural diagram is shown and explained in Figure 1.

Figure 1: ENVRI-FAIR catalogue of services basic architecture. The underlying idea is that any Research Infrastructure provides access, ultimately, to data, and that metadata is used to search, discover and contextualize the data. Then, the data searched through metadata is made available through “services”. Although the definition of services is still under discussion in TF1, two main modalities for accessing the services were identified: a) through Web-Apis, for instance restful web-services, that can be accessed by machines and that are easily upgradable to be FAIR as they are potentially machine-readable and machine-understandable, and b) through Portals, mostly accessible by humans, but yet an asset providing access to the datasets.

During the meeting, an informal survey with the attendees was carried out, and the following was found out:

APIs technologies in place:

- RESTFUL WEBAPIS
- ERDDAP services
- Opendap

Metadata Standards in place

- OAI-PMH ISO 19139
- Geonetwork (restful apis+oai-pmh)

Data formats in place:

- DATA (csv, JSON, netcdf, ASCII, nasa-ames)
- METADATA

The basic idea in this context is that both services implemented through Web-APis and those implemented by means of portals, are candidate objects to be part of the ENVRI-FAIR service catalogue. The goal of the catalogue is therefore to map, at least as first-attempt exercise, only services and other high-level objects.

Although it is still under discussion, an agreed point is that it will not map all the metadata available at the RIs specific metadata catalogues level.

In order to carry out the required work, TF1 decided to have regular meetings.

All documentation, including members of the task force, relevant documents, minutes from the meeting, is available in the project intranet (Redmine system) at this URL

https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/task-forces/wiki/1_ENVRI_Catalogue_of_Services

(accessed on 26/06/2020)

4 Progress on the design of the service catalogue

TF1 continued its work after the ENVRI-FAIR meeting through periodic teleconferences where a number of key milestones were achieved. They are listed below:

1. Key achievement 1: RIs involvement through use cases

A spreadsheet for collecting use cases of potential "resources" (i.e. services, portals, datasets or other assets) was prepared and filled in by all relevant stakeholders¹.

This spreadsheet has several tabs, and the main objective is to guide RIs through a process that will ultimately lead to a specific technical definition of their assets to be included into the catalogue in a step-by-step way. So, while tab 1 "RIs" in the spreadsheet is just a first survey of available RIs providing services, the tab "CATALOGUE USE CASE" is an attempt to map more technically all the services (both web services and portals) available from RIs.

The collection of these information was carried out in a bottom-up way, in order to guarantee that a general consensus about the contents and technical solutions adopted was reached.

2. Key achievement 2: Definition of the objectives and catalogue schema first agreements

During its work, the TF1 was asked by the project coordinator to provide a document that described objectives, the status, the progress and future work of Tfl.

The document was written collaboratively on the basis of a draft document provide by the TF1 leader (Daniele Bailo) and is reported in Annex 1 in this document.

Drafting the document required intense discussions where potential solutions, technical details, metadata related issues were investigated.

The creation of the document led to define CERIF as a potential candidate for the ENVRI-FAIR catalogue of services. Also, this work had the merit of acknowledge the entire group on outstanding issues like heterogeneity of metadata, interoperability with the European Open Science Cloud.

3. Key achievement 3: leveraging on existing solutions

Although intense discussions were carried out around the question "what metadata standard would be better", a pragmatic approach was agreed all along the meetings. In this sense, there is a general consensus about leveraging on existing solutions that might lead quickly towards a proof-of-concept implementation, which will make the entire discussion more grounded to reality, thus ensuring that the efforts dedicated to the development of the catalogue in the task force are well grounded and capitalized, so to end up in a real catalogue at the end of the project.

In order to follow the proposed approach, it has agreed to make a first attempt by reusing the work done in the EPOS RI, which already implemented a CERIF metadata catalogue for the mapping of services.

5 Proposed solution

The architecture of the proposed solution is therefore borrowed by the EPOS ICS-C Research Infrastructure architecture, reported in Figure 2.

¹ Spredahseet available at: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1-9srcD58uZYjmahaKBXW4YeWU6QKAMz7ZGenW8wCCFA/edit#gid=456291350>, last accessed on 26/06/2020

Figure 2: EPOS Integrated Core Services - Central HUB basic architecture. The picture represents the basic architecture of the EPOS RIs. The main component, with respect to the main topic of the current document, is the CERIF metadata catalogue included in the ICS purple layer. Such metadata schema is rich enough to store details about the services provided by the underlying system, TCS (thematic Core Services) in the EPOS jargon, which correspond to the RIs in ENVRI-FAIR.

The architecture is described in detail elsewhere², and it is out of the scope of this document to go into the details of this description.

The main idea is that RIs within ENVRI-FAIR can describe services or portal (represented by the “TCS” yellow boxes in Figure 2) by means of metadata that can ultimately be ingested into the ICS-C metadata catalogue, which is based on the CERIF metadata model and ingests metadata in a DCAT-AP application profile to which other metadata formats may readily be converted.

Such solution found a good consensus within TF1 meetings, and is likely to be implemented as proof-of-concept in order to be further validated and investigated.

6 Conclusion

In a period of approximately 6 months TF1 has done a landscape survey, discussed roadmap plans for the ENVRI RIs and concluded on a way forward involving a rich canonical metadata catalog to permit interoperation among ENVRI RIs and with EOSC.

The next steps involve:

- (1) Mapping RI metadata formats to the canonical metadata model;
- (2) Mapping the canonical metadata model to the services catalog of EOSC.

7 Annex 1 – ENVRI-FAIR WP5 TF1 Catalogue Task Force Document

7.1 Objectives

The main objective of this Task Force is to agree and implement a metadata catalogue schema and associated management services, with the aim of describing and providing access to assets available from the ENVRI RIs. This can be potentially used as input to the ENVRI- EOSC catalogue, after appropriate transformation to match EOSC requirements.

² All documentation available here: <https://github.com/epos-eu/documentation>

7.2 Approach

7.2.1 Heterogeneity of Research Infrastructures

Existing research infrastructures in the framework of ENVRI-FAIR are part of a common landscape but with consistent differences in terms of:

- (i) presenting and accessing datasets, which span from machine-readable solutions (e.g. services with RESTful webAPIs) to human-accessible only portals;
- (ii) datasets (and other assets) and some description of their actual contents:
 - formats, spanning from binary files, to .csv and proprietary formats, or in some cases well defined standards (e.g. NetCDF);
 - as well as the semantics (formal descriptions of the fields therein) that are key to the interoperability
- (iii) way of accessing datasets and other assets e.g. services and consequent metadata description, spanning from location-based search to parameter-based selections and/or 'keyword' terms or free-text terms;
- (iv) resources of interests, spanning from services, datasets, to source codes or documents
- (v) audiences served, spanning from individual researchers, collaborations and RIs, to automated harvesters and linked virtual research environments

In such a complex landscape, the common goal is to achieve interoperability through semantic and technical harmonization driven by FAIR principles.

7.2.2 Achieving Interoperability

Interoperability can be obtained by following FAIR principles and adopting appropriate technologies to implement them. In particular, a rich metadata schema is necessary to accommodate the existing complexity. This schema must also be able to facilitate representing information related to resources (services, datasets, codes etc.), publications, persons, organizations, facilities, equipment, authorization details and others, in a machine-readable and machine-understandable way.

7.2.3 Rich Metadata Catalogue

Simply combining the metadata from the RIs is not enough, because they need to be harmonized. This is the function of a canonical superset-rich metadata catalogue that can represent descriptions of services from RIs implementing rich metadata. This will ensure actual machine readability and machine understandability, together with formal syntax and declared semantics.

Processes to fill the homogeneous catalogue with heterogeneous individual information by RIs are also required. The catalogue will be filled with existing resources and assets, which will be represented by metadata records describing, datasets, services, workflows/tools, e-services and other assets such as equipment.

7.2.4 EOSC Interoperability

In this framework, interoperability with the EOSC catalogue is intended as a two-way process: from the ENVRI-FAIR catalogue of services to the EOSC catalogue (ENVRI-to-EOSC), and vice versa (EOSC-to-ENVRI). The ENVRI-to-EOSC process will guarantee that **ENVRI is the entry point for providing details about ENV RIs, that can be in turn harvested by the EOSC catalogue.**

The EOSC-to-ENVRI process guarantees that users searching the EOSC catalogue will invoke services from ENV RIs, and that the EOSC catalogue can be used by ENVRI for making usage of EOSC resources.

Both processes require technical procedures for mapping metadata, and this is to be discussed within this task force

7.2.5 Governance

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) includes ethics, gender balance, governance, open access, public engagement, and science and education. This should inform the processes around the metadata

catalogue, which in turn define what information is required in the catalogue to fulfil those processes. Security and privacy are key aspects within governance.

7.3 Current work

7.3.1 Landscaping exercise

Before proposing fit-for-purpose technical solutions, we are undergoing a landscaping exercise which will report on the status of all RIs within the TF1, concentrating on the methodologies used to access their resources (datasets, software codes etc.).

7.3.2 Capturing RIs heterogeneity

The above exercise, still ongoing but progressing well, is showing that many infrastructures provide access to their assets by means of services, others use only GUIs for human interactions, and mixed scenarios are also present (e.g. computational through web-APIs). This heterogeneity will be captured in a common canonical superset-rich metadata description.

7.3.3 Convergence on the definition of “services”

The ongoing discussion is also showing the need for a common jargon, especially concerning key words such as “services”, which are interpreted differently according to the background. In this context we propose “services” to be used not only with (a) its pure technical meaning, that is to say RESTful or SOAP services that provide access in a programmatic way to resources, but also (b) in a looser way, everything that implements a functionality that serves for a purpose (e.g. a map-GUI to browse a dataset).

7.3.4 Convergence on metadata required for the catalogue

Initial discussions pointed out the inadequacy of the metadata schema proposed in the context of EOSC Hub, inherited from eInfracentral, as it is tailored for describing computational-like eInfrastructures rather than RIs that provide data. ENVRIplus concluded with trials of two homogenizing metadata schemes, namely CKAN, as used by EUDAT, and CERIF, as used by EPOS. ENV RIs were invited to try these solutions and conclude what they wanted for any common catalogue. In this sense, an existing, well-tested option is on the table, that is to say the CERIF metadata catalogue already used by the EPOS RIs.

7.4 Conclusion

TF1 has made good progress. We now face much work to characterize the metadata catalogues of the RIs, discover commonalities and differences and move towards a common catalogue schema.

7.5 Annex A – TF1 Members

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